

Classical Newar Annotation Manual

Part II - Segmentation & POS tagging

Alexander O'Neill & Marieke Meelen

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Version control

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1. Introduction

Our annotation philosophy prioritises description over analysis to facilitate future research. For words, nouns are split as much as is possible without introducing ambiguity, individual verbs are kept intact, but serial verbs are separated. In terms of Part of Speech (POS) tagging, morphological information is noted conservatively to allow for analysis of the changes in constructions over time. More specifically, our philosophy for word segmentation is that case markers are split from their preceding noun phrases and words and words without case markers are kept intact and marked for their POS. Regarding style, this guide puts all Newar text in bold, Sanskrit text in bold italics, and translations of terms in quotation marks. Full names of POS tags are given in bold and underlined below the tag name.

2. Segmentation

This section has rules on word segmentation. Case markers in Newar cannot simply be split, as they contain sequences of characters that are quite common and thus ambiguous. Therefore, in our word segmentation section, we first identify unambiguous case markers that can be split without giving rise to later difficulties and then ambiguous case markers that, depending on their frequency, are either (1) split and reconnected when they are *not* case markers (i.e., are part of noun phrases proper), or (2) kept connected to the noun phrases and then split later when they are, in fact, case markers. For these later segmentations, we developed a list of rule-based corrections in an *Ongoing Segmentation Errors, Questions, and Comments* document. We then apply these rules after a round of manual corrections, meaning the next time we encounter these “errors”, they are segmented and tagged properly.

Word Segmentation

This section lists unambiguous segments first, followed by their POS. These are always split from noun phrases. Unambiguous case markers are split from case markers in certain cases that can only fully be understood by examining the segmentation script. More details about particular case markers are in the appropriate sections for those case markers in the “Automatic POS-tagging” section.

List of Unambiguous Case Markers

- yākēna** /case.abl
- pani** /case.abs.h.pl
- tva** /case.abs.nh.pl
- mista**, -**mistaṃ** /case.dat.nh.pl
- panistaṃ**, -**panista**, -**panita**, -**staṃ**, or -**sta** /case.dat.h.pl
- seṃ**, -**sena** /case.erg.h
- taṣeṃ**, -**toṣeṃ**, -**tasena**, -**tosena** /case.erg.nh.pl
- paniṣeṃ**, -**panisena**, -**panisyana**, -**panisenāṃ**, -**panisyanāṃ** /case.erg.h.pl
- tasa**, -**tosa**, -**misa** /case.gen.nh.pl
- panisa** /case.gen.h.pl
- ske**, -**sake** /case.loc.an
- paniske**, -**panisake** /case.loc.pl
- misva**, -**misvo**, -**misava**, -**misavo** /case.ass.nh.pl
- panisva**, -**panisvo**, -**panisava**, or -**panisavo** /case.ass.h.pl

List of Ambiguous Case Markers

Underlined cases are the more likely option out of two.

-ø /case.abs

case.erg (-n, -na, or -m (anusvāra)) usually used for case.abl, will occur at the end of regular nouns (esp. Loans Skt)

-ta = case.abs.nh.pl and case.dat will occur in verbs or loans Skt

-to case.abs.nh.pl will also occur in verbs or loans Skt

-sa case.gen and case.loc.inan (95% of the time, this is case.loc.inan)

-ke, -yāke case.loc.an will also occur in verbs

-yā case.gen will occur in verbs (this ambiguity is closer to 50/50)

-va, -vo, -o case.ass will also occur in loans Skt verbs

-yātam, -yātā case.dat, (these are typical verb endings and independent verbs)

-tā case.dat will occur in verbs and loans Skt.

Sentence Segmentation

Segmenting sentences is an important task creating annotated corpora as they often form the basic unit of calculating frequencies, e.g. 'How many sentences have word order X?'. In Newar this is a non-trivial task since original punctuation in the manuscript in the form of *daṇḍa* | and double *daṇḍa* || does not always correspond to conventional sentence boundaries. Utterance boundaries (<utt>) are therefore inserted automatically after *daṇḍa* | and double *daṇḍa* ||, but will need to be manually corrected in cases where the resulting utterance does not contain a main clause predicate. When using edited texts, we follow the punctuation of the editor and add <utt> after full stops.

Although the main protocol of having one and only one main clause predicate works well in most instances, there are cases where automatic sentence segmentation would yield the wrong result for instance when *daṇḍa* boundaries in the manuscripts do not correspond to main clauses, but split subordinate clauses from main clauses instead. In those and other cases we manually correct the segmentation by deleting and/or inserting sentence boundaries when appropriate.

One particularly complex case that deserves special attention in indirect speech in the middle of what could be considered a main clause. Ergative arguments are then often continued as (null) subjects of the clause following the (in)direct speech + verbs/marks to indicate the end of the direct speech as shown in examples a-c where an utterance boundary of the previous sentence is followed by a noun phrase in the ergative is followed by (in)direct speech and a form of the grammaticalised verb **dhak**, which is tagged as **v.dhak**. This can function as a main clause by itself. However, it can also be followed by a converb, creating a subordinate clause, which is why no utterance boundary is inserted in sentences like b) below. Finally, **v.dhak** can be followed by a finite verb, again turning it into a main clause like c) after which an utterance boundary is added.

- a) <utt> 'The king.ERG, "DIRECT SPEECH" said/v.dhak, <utt> [Null argument] went home." <utt> → pattern: v.dhak <utt> [next clause] <utt>
- b) <utt> 'The king.ERG, "DIRECT SPEECH"/v.dhak having said/cv.ant, [Null argument] went home." <utt> → pattern: v.dhak + cv.X [next clause] <utt>
- c) <utt> 'The king.ERG, "DIRECT SPEECH"/v.dhak said/v.perf, <utt> [Null argument] went home." <utt> → pattern: v.dhak + v.X <utt> [next clause] <utt>

3. POS tagging

The following section lists POS tags that can be applied in level 4 headings; level 3 headings indicate their category in alphabetical order. Descriptions that follow the tags give examples of terms that should be tagged accordingly or of the forms terms take that should be tagged with these POS tags. These are not exhaustive and can be expanded where necessary. If, at any point, further refinement is required, these can be amended or expanded.

Adjectives

adj

Adjectives. These come to the left of nouns and have no case, plural markers, or postpositions, which are added to the last component of the noun phrase (though beware of unmarked absolutes). E.g. **tava/adj rājā/n na/case.erg** “by the *great* king.”

Adverbs

adv.conj

Conjunctive adverbs. This tag is used for words that join two independent clauses, typically introducing a sentence. These include words with the sense of “then” or “thereupon,” such as: **thathe** (var. **thathem**) and its variations like **thathena**, **thathenam**, **thathenantu**, **thathenanakam**, **thathēñale**, **thathēñele**, **thathegva** (var. **thathigva**), **thathemgva** (var. **thathimḡva**) or **thathegvamha** (var. **thathigvamha**) and **thathemgvamha** (var. **thathimḡvamha**); this also includes forms of **athe** (“then”) and its variations like **athem**, **athena**, **athenam**, **athenta julasanvam**, **athabā**, **athavā**, and **atha**. This tag is also applied to words with the sense of “again” or “furthermore,” such as: **hanvam**, **hana**, **hānam**, **hanom**, **hanam** (which can also be an adv.freq) and **hanakam**, **hanakanam**; it is also used to tag **yathenam**; **mebathem**, **mebanam**, and **lithem**.

adv.correl

Correlative adverbs. This tag is used for situations where a relative adverb (adv.rel) on the stem **go-**, e.g. **go/adv.rel** (“which”), or its variants, e.g. **gana/adv.rel** (“where”), precedes a corresponding adverb based on the stem **va-** (“that”) or **a-** (“that,” distant). An example of such a sentence would be **gana/adv.rel chimisem hayā ana/adv.correl tolatāva thāthiva**, “Where (**gana**) you found [them], leave [them] there (**ana**).”

adv.deg

Adverbs of degree. This tag is used for words that express extent, intensify meaning, or weaken meaning. They include words such as **atī** (“exceedingly”), **gā** (“enough”), **thimña** (“such”), **theni** (“out of this amount”), **juyaka** (“satisfactorily”), **jaka**, (“only”), and **melako** (“as much as needed”).

adv.dir

Directional adverbs. This tag is used for words that specify direction. They include words such as **kva** (“below;” var. **ko**, **kum**), and its modifications **kvadu**, **kvane**, **kvasa**, **kvadum**; **thadum** (“above”), **agrasa** (“before”), **li** (“behind”), and its modifications **lisem**, **livane**, **liva**, and **liva liva**

(note: these can also be understood as adv.temp, i.e. “after”), and **lihā** (“back,” var. **lihāṃ**); **anā** (“there”).

adv.dur

Adverbs of duration. This tag is used for words that specify the length of time something happened or lasted. They include **tā** and **cirakālaṃ** (“a long time”) and **khaṃchi** (“some time/a moment” var. **khachi**).

adv.freq

Adverbs of frequency. This tag is used for words that describe how often something occurs, either definitely or indefinitely. They include **sadā** (“always”) and **hana** (“again,” vars. **hanaṃ** and **hānaṃ**; note: this can also be used as an adv.conj).

adv.inter

Interrogative adverbs. This tag is used for question words corresponding to why, where, and how. They include **chān** (“why,” the equivalent of the modern **chāy**, var. **chāñā**, modf. **chāñāna**), **ganā** (“where,” var. **ge**) and its modifications such as **ganāna** (var. **gena**), and **gathe** (“how,” “of what kind,” var. **gathem**, **gathiṇa**, modfs. **gathiṃgva**, **gathiṃmha**).

adv.man

Adverbs of manner. This tag is used for words that describe how an action is carried out. In classical Newar, these are usually based on Sanskrit nouns with an ergative ending, whereas in Sanskrit, the base noun takes an anusvara to make them indeclinable accusative adverbs (E.g. Skt. *sāvadhāna* (“attentive;” declinable) → *sāvadhānaṃ* (“attentively;” indeclinable) = Nw. **sāvadhānana** or **sāvadhānaṃ** (“attentively”). This can be understood as the instrumental ergative (e.g., “with attention”). Still, to avoid losing the indication of adverbial sense (e.g., “attentively”), the ergative markers are not segmented from their roots (in which case, such a term would rather have been labelled **sāvadhāna**/n “attention” **na**/case.erg). When used in the sense of “such” or “in this matter,” the word **tathe** (var. **thathye**) fits into this category, rather than into the category of adv.conj where it otherwise goes. Of similar sense is **thukā** (“as it is known,” “as you see,” or “evidently”).

adv.place

Adverbs of place. This tag is used for words that tell us about an aspect of location associated with the action of a verb. It includes words such as **anyatrasa** (“elsewhere”), **agraśa** (“in the fore”), **sameta** (“together with”), and **the** (“here,” var. **thi**).

adv.reason

Adverbs of reason. This tag is used for words that express the sense of “because of...” It includes **saṃkoca** and the Sanskritic **tatkāraṇaṃ** “for that reason.”

adv.rel

Relative adverbs. This tag is used for words that introduce a relative clause. It includes words that are formed on the step **go-** (“which,” var. **ga-**), e.g. **gana** (“where”) and **gathem** (“how”), with the correlative counterparts **ana**/adv.correl (“there”) and **athem**/adv.correl (“thus”). This also includes **amathem** (“like that”).

adv.temp

Temporal adverbs. This tag is used for words that describe when an action is carried out. It includes words such as **thani** (“today”), **liva** (“after,” “later”), and **ñhavayā** (“prior ...”)

Cases

The following section provides the POS tags we use to tag case markers. As discussed in the postposition section below, these fundamentally find their origin in postpositions (Noonan 2008), and therefore, for information structural purposes, they are treated as postpositions but tagged as cases for purposes of accessibility and consistency with existing literature on Newar grammar. These tags are applied to case markers segmented from their modified nouns. For the exceptional situation of the singular absolutive case, which does not have a case marker, see the section for case.abs. This section, moreover, provides a brief overview of the use cases for each of these cases—the use cases for these markers naturally do not perfectly align with the latinized names that are used to name them. Thus care should be observed in understanding the usage of each, as they differ from their apparent equivalents in other languages. Examples of markers for each case are given in their descriptions; however, owing to the tendency for orthographic irregularity in Classical Newar MSS, please note that these examples cannot be exhaustive. Here, the more extensive descriptions are given at the first instance of a case marker, and related cases are indented to show their relationship to cases listed previously (e.g. case.abs is the first marker of the absolutives discussed, and the case.abs.h.pl is second, and so is indented).

case.abl

Ablative case. This is used to indicate case markers denoting ablation proper, cause or reason, and, in a few cases, as a locative (Jørgensen, §29 and §30 d, e, and f). In essence, it takes the ergative marker, i.e. **-n**, **-na**, or **-ṃ** (var. **-saṃ**, **-seṃ**, **-syam**). However, for a specifically ablative sense, **-yākena** is used. Perhaps because it is rare in the Classical Newar *Vetālapañcaviṃśati*, Otter does not include it in his course book.

case.abs

Absolutive case. This tag is used for words that act as the patient (logical object) of a transitive/controlled verb or argument (subject) of an intransitive/non-controlled verb—whereas, in a clause with a transitive/controlled verb, the agent is marked for case.erg. Words in the absolutive take zero marker (**-Ø**) in the singular and inanimate plural. Therefore, we do not tag such absolutive nouns (only those which are case.abs.h.pl or case.abs.nh.pl. Jørgensen (§23) calls this the nominative or casus indefinitus, and notes the following eight use cases for the absolutive: (1) the subject of intransitive verbs, (2) the object of transitive verbs, (3) the accusative of effect, (4) as an essivus, (5) as an accusativus modalis, (6) to denote time and space, (7) an allative, and (8) as a cognate object). See the appropriate section for examples.

case.abs.h

Singular honourific animate absolutive case. This tag is used for the Old Newar (12th to 14th C) **-sa** when used in the absolutive sense (e.g. “... kvachem pāla bhārosa jvaṃñā.” “The Pāla Bhāro of Kvāche was captured.”).

case.abs.h.pl

Plural honourific animate absolute case. This tag is used for plural honorific animate nouns, which usually have **-pani** added to the noun stem.

case.abs.nh.pl

Plural non-honourific animate absolute case. This tag is used for plural non-honourific animate nouns, which usually have **-ta** (var. **-to**, **-tva**) added to the noun stem.

case.ass

Associative case. This tag is for case markers denoting the associative case. It is used primarily for animate nouns and the first and second-person pronouns. Otter (§41) says that “its function corresponds to that of the English preposition ‘(together) with’.” Jørgensen (§31-2) notes that it can also be used in the following constructions: with **biruddha** “objectionable to,” (e.g. **lokavo biruddha**, “objectionable to people”) and **sama** or **tulya** “like” (e.g. **chuva sama julo**, “he became like a mouse (**chu**)”) (Otter §41, notes that **tulya** can be used with inanimate nouns). He also notes the existence of the double sociative with the sense “both X and Y.” Both Otter and Jørgensen call it the “Sociative.” It is marked by **-va** (vars. **-vo**, **-o**). In old Newar (e.g. *Gopāla*), we see **-savo**.

case.ass.nh.pl

Plural non-honourific associative case. This tag is used for the marker **-misava** (vars. **-misavo**, **-misva**, **misvo**).

case.ass.h.pl

Plural honourific associative case. This tag is used for the marker **-panisava** (vars. **-panisavo**, **-panisva**, **-panisvo**).

case.dat

Dative case. This tag is used for case markers denoting the dative case, which marks the third argument. This is almost only found with animate nouns. Jørgensen (§27) notes the following four use cases of the dative: (1) as an indirect object, (2) as a direct object, particularly in later MSS, (3) as a dative of purpose, and (4) as an allative. There is no honourific status marker in the singular. Its case markers are **-ta** (var. **-tā**, **-taṃ**, **-to**, **-toṃ**) and **yātaṃ** (var. **-yāta**, **-yātā**).

case.dat.nh.pl

Plural non-honourific dative. The non-honourific plural dative case is marked by **-mista** (var. **mistaṃ**).

case.dat.h.pl

Plural honourific dative. The honourific plural dative case is marked by **-panista** (var. **-panistaṃ**) or **-sta** (var. **-staṃ**).

case.erg

Ergative case. This tag is used for case markers denoting the agent of transitive verbs (finite or non-finite). The ergative doubles as an instrumental, especially with inanimate nouns. In singular

non-honourific (and some honourific) contexts, it is marked by **-n**, **-na**, **-ṃ** (anusvāra), or **-naṃ**. In some non-honourific cases, **-seṃ** (var. **-syam**, **-sam**) are used, but otherwise, these are honourific.

case.erg.h

Honourific ergative case. This tag is used for the honourific ergative case marker. Its markers can be seen in non-honourific cases, they are more common for honourific nouns. They are **-seṃ** (var. **-syam**, **-sam**, **-sena**, **-syena**, **-senam**, **-syanam**, **-sana**),

case.erg.nh.pl

Plural non-honourific ergative case. This tag is used for plural non-honourific ergative nouns. They are marked by **-taseṃ** (var. **-toseṃ**, **-tasena**, and **-tosenā**).

case.erg.h.pl

Plural honourific ergative case. This tag is used for plural honourific ergative nouns. They are marked **-paniseṃ** (**-panisena**, **-panisyana**, **-panisyam**, **-polasyam**, and **-polasyena**).

case.gen

Genitive Case. This tag is used for case markers denoting the genitive, which is signified by **-yā**, which is usually used in the singular, and sometimes **-sa**, particularly for animate/honourific words in the singular and the plural in general. The modern Newar **-gu** (var. **-gū**) is sometimes found to take on this function, although this is actually an agreement marker.

Otter (§31) notes that it can express the notion “to have.”

Jørgensen notes the following nine use cases for the genitive in Classical Newar: (1) possessive (e.g. **mantriya kāya**, “the minister’s son”), (2) subjective (e.g. **bhatiya bhaya**, “the cat’s fear”), (3) objective (e.g. **dhanaya lobha**, “greed for riches”) (4) descriptive (e.g. **prakarayā śastr**, “weapons of many kinds”), (5) partitive (e.g., **uḷ ḍākinisa chamha**, “one of these ḍākinīs”), (6) genitivus generis (e.g., **naḃā bhaṇḍāra**, “an iron vessel”), (7) genitive used with verbs with a sense of possession (e.g. “to have” with **daya** (e.g. **thva baniyāyā ekaputrī dava**, “this merchant had one daughter”) and “to become the property of with **juya** (e.g. **rājya dhana sampattiḷ thva brāhmaṇayā julo**, “the kingdom and the treasures have become the property of the brāhmaṇa”), as well as metaphor (e.g., **pakṣipaniṣa ahaṃkāra juyāo coṇā**, “the birds had become haughty”), (8) genitive used with verbs to express something like a state (e.g. **barakhunisa lobha vaṇāva**, “the pigeons, having become greedy...”), and (9) genitive as a derived noun (e.g., **thao cheyāpani**, “his housemates”).

case.gen.h

Singular honourific genitive case. This tag is used for the singular honourific genitive **-sa** in Old Newar, which may be derived from the Sanskrit **-sya** (e.g.,

case.gen.nh.pl

Plural non-honourific genitive case. This tag is for case markers such as **-tasa** (var. **-tosa**) or **-misa**.

case.gen.h.pl

Plural honourific genitive case. This tag is used for case markers such as **-panisa**, **-pisa**, and **-polayā**.

case.loc.inan

Inanimate locative case. This tag is used for case markers denoting the inanimate locative case. In classical Newar, the locative expresses location or direction; for its peculiarities when used with animate nouns, see below. It is indicated by **-sa** (var. **-saṃ** (rare)).

Jørgensen notes the following eight use cases for the locative in Classical Newar: (1) locative proper, (2) the locative in verbal constructions (i.e., **kaya** “to take Y from X-loc,” **khuya** “to steal Y from X-loc,” **sene** “to learn Y of X-loc,” **phone** “to beg Y of X-loc,” and **ñene** “to ask Y of X-loc”), (3) allative (e.g., **mantriya chesa vanam** “he went to the minister’s house”), (4) time (e.g. **rātrisa**, “at night”), (5) dative (**rājāyāke svapna bilam**, “he gave a dream to the king”), (6) as part of verbal constructions (e.g. **abhyāsa yāya**, “to study”), (7) miscellaneous use cases (e.g. **chanake coṅa kauli**, “the cowries, which are in your possession”), and (8) partitive genitive (e.g. **jī bosa chi bo**, “one part out of ten”).

case.loc.an

Animate locative case. Note that with the animate locative in Classical Newar can also express possession and mark an addressee of certain verba dicendi. The animate locative case markers are **-sake** (var. **-sake**), **-ke**, or **-yāke**.

case.loc.pl

Plural locative case. The plural locative is only used for animate, honourific nouns. Its marker is **-panisake** (var. **-paniske**).

Classifiers

This section lists the tags that we use for Classical Newar classifiers. Classifiers provide information about nouns, and are used in the case of (1) numeral classifiers, (2) as agreement markers, and (3) as nominalisers. They can give information about the kind of thing being referred to in terms of animacy and type. For numerals, every numeral must be marked with a classifier or the generic particle (**cs.inan**), and they can give information about the shape or type of object (e.g. round, houses, etc.). Agreement markers are optional in Classical Newar and are usually the generic **cs.anim** or **cs.inan**. The same generic classifiers can be used as nominalisers and give deictic emphasis.

cs.anim

Animate classifier. This tag is used for the animate classifier, **-mham** (vars. **-mha**, **-mhā**).¹ Nazalation of **cs.anim** does not necessarily indicate ergativity. Doubling of the **cs.anim** usually indicates that the preceding numeral is ordinal, e.g. **nimhamha** = the second [person].

¹ Some Romanizations, e.g. Jørgensen, use **hma**. In fact, both **hma** and **mha** are represented in Newar Pracalit and Newar Devanagari with the same ligatures.

cs.inan

Generic inanimate classifier. This tag is used for the generic classifier for inanimate numerals, agreement, or nominalisation, **-gu** (vars. **-guli**, **-go**). As an example of its use for nominalisation: **yeyā**/v.perf.part (“wished”), but **yeyāguli** (“that which was wished”).

cs.round

Round object classifier. This tag is used for the classifier for round objects, **-go** (var. **gva**) or **-gola** (var. **goḍa**).

cs.abs

Abstract concept classifier. This tag is used for the classifier for abstract concepts, **-tā** (var. **-tām**)

cs.time

Unit of time classifier. This tag is used for classifiers that indicate a unit of time, e.g., **-nhu** (“days”), **-da** (var. **-dam**, “years”), and **-lā** (“months”). **pola** (var. **pvala**) is used to indicate times of action or numbers of times (e.g. **nipola** “two times”).

cs.storey

Storey number classifier. This tag is used for the classifier **-ta** that indicates the storey of a building, e.g. **neta** (“second storey”), **svata** (“third storey”).

cs.flat

Flat object classifier. This tag is used for the flat object classifier **-pā**.

cs.long

Long object classifier. This tag is used for classifiers that indicate long objects or weapons, e.g., **pu** (for long and round or thin things) and **-ka** (for long things related to hands, such as a hand itself or fingers).

Demonstratives

d.dem

Demonstratives. This tag is used for the deictic pronouns **thva** (vars. **tho**, **thu**, **tha**, **thvasa**; “this”), **āma** (vars. **āmo**, **amo**; “that” (near-listener)), **va** (vars. **vo**, **o**, **u**, “that” (distant); note that this is sometimes an adv.correl), and **huhum** (remote). To these can be added various of the case markers or derivative suffixes.

d.quant

Demonstrative quantifiers. This tag is used for terms meaning “many” such as **aneka** (var. **anega**), **vividha**, **sakala** (var. **sakalem**) and **dakva** (“all”, var. **dāko**, **dākva**), and every (**patim**).

Numerals

num

Newar numerals. This tag is used for Newar numerals not represented by Arabic or Sanskrit numerals, e.g., cha, ni, sva, pe, etc. Classifiers are added to these numerals, not to Arabic or Sanskrit numerals.

num.ar

Arabic numerals. This tag is used for Arabic numerals 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 0. Note that an Arabic numeral after a word can also mean a repetition of that word so that the total number of the word equals the numeral, e.g. **śrī 3**, i.e. **śrī śrī śrī**.

num.skt

Sanskrit numerals. This tag is used for Sanskrit numerals, written out in full. These are often used to formally express the ordinal (which otherwise needs to be formed by a doubling of a numeral classifier), e.g. **viṃśati**. It is also used for badly spelt or garbled numbers that appear to have entered Newar but are not native Newar numbers, e.g. **tirākha** (from *trītyā*, third).

Postpositions

While in Tibetan, we do not distinguish between postpositions and case markers, tokens that we tag as postpositions in Classical Newar are not case markers. However, Noonan argues that Newar case markers, and Bodish case markers in general, were originally distinct nouns that transitioned into demoninal postpositions and case clitics (Noonan 2008). We tag postpositions and cases distinctly for consistency with existing literature on Newar grammar, but for information structural purposes, we treat them both as postpositional phrases. As Otter discusses (Otter 2021, §69), labelling these markers as postpositions is a convention. These postpositions are separate words (many of which are of Sanskrit origin) that can govern words marked with case markers, clitics of focus, emphasis, interrogation, or topic markers.

post.abs

Postpositions that govern the absolutive case. This tag is used for postpositions that follow nouns or case markers in the absolutive case. They include **to** (var. **toṃ**; “towards”), **tohona** (“in the guise of”), **them** (vars. **the**, **thiṃ**; “as,” “like”), **se** (vars. **syā**, **sye**; “as if,” “like”), **duhā** (“into”), **nimistana** (var. **nimistina**, **nimittina**, **nimirttina**; “for the sake of”), **belasa** (“at the time”), **sahita** (var. **sahitaṃ**; “together with”), **niseṃ** (var. **nisyam**; “since”). Some of these are also often seen following the genitive, with the sense of “for the sake of X” (with **nimittina**) or with a verb (particularly v.n) with the sense of “for the sake of doing X” (again, with **nimittina**). Some which generally, but not always, are governed by the absolutive, include **prati** from Sanskrit, which can be used as “per” (e.g. **mīm mham prati...**, “... per person”), **thyaṃgva** “to the level of” (e.g. **...deśa ko thyaṃgva**, “to the level of the city/country”), and **udeśanā** “with the intention of.” So, it may be that the absolutive postpositions are simply more flexible in their use cases.

post.gen

Postpositions that govern the genitive case. This tag is used for postpositions that follow a genitive case marker. They include **agraśa** (“before”), **ñhavane** (“in the presence of;” this can also govern the

locative case, but since this is rare and has the same meaning, it is still tagged post.gen for now), **duvane** (var. **du**; “inside”), **li** (“after;” this is also possible after the ergative but is still tagged post.gen, and of course also comprises the cv.anter, about which, see the converb section), **samīpasa** (“nearby,” “towards”), **sinam** (var. **sinom**; “more than”). In the *Gopālarājavamśavalī*, **nimatina** appears as a post.gen, whereas, normally, it would be a post.abs.

post.ass

Postpositions that govern the associative case. This tag is used for postpositions that follow an associative case marker. They include **tule** (var. **tulya**; “comparable”) and **nāpaṃ** (vars. **napaṃ**, **nāpā**; “with”).

Clitics

cl.focus

Focus clitics. This tag is used for clitics that are emphatic in meaning or that give the sense of exclusive focus. They include the emphatic clitics **-aṃ** (var. **-naṃ**, easily confused with case.erg), **-toṃ**, **-to**, **-tu**, **-ni**, and the exclusive focus clitics of Sanskrit derivation, **mātra** and **mātrana**. In the *Gopālarājavamśavalī*, we also see **dhāre** used as an emphatic particle.

cl.inter

Interrogative clitics. This tag is used for the **lā** clitic, which is used as a particle of interrogation. It is sometimes seen with a short vowel **la** or as **rā/ra**.

cl.top

Topic clitic. This tag is used for topic markers formed from the base verb **juya** (“to become”), with the meaning of “as for X.” These include a normal verbal form, such as **julaṃ**/v.perf.past (var. **julo**), in which case context dictates the correct tag, whereas others only appear to appear as topic markers, such as **julasā**, **julasāṃ**, **jusāṃ**, and **jukāle**. The form **julasāṃ** followed by another **julasāṃ** later in the sentence takes on the meaning “whether... or.”

Nouns

n

Noun. This tag is used for nouns.

n.prop

Proper nouns. This tag is used for proper nouns: place and person names. In the case of some editions, these will be capitalised.

Pronouns

p.anaphor

Anaphoric pronoun. This tag is used for a pronoun that has the sense of “the aforementioned,” it is **thvate**, also **thvatesa** (this appears to have a loc suffix, i.e. at the aforementioned).

p.correl

Correlative pronoun. This tag is used for correlative pronouns, in which case, they should have a relative counterpart. They can take case markers. These are **va** (“that;” correlative of **su**, **gona** (var. **gvana**), or **gva**; when animate, **mha** should precede the case marker), **uguli** (“that much;” correlative of some uses of **chu**), **e e** (“there;” correlative of **ge ge** “where”), **athe** (var. **athem**; “thus;” correlative of **gathe** (var. **gathem**; “how”)), **valo** (var. **olo**; “this;” correlative of **gvalo**, “which”), **valoto** (var. **oloto**; “that;” “that many;” correlative of **gvaloto**), **ana** (“there;” correlative of **gana**, “where”). The word **thathiña** (var. **thathim**) is often used as a correlative (“such a”), as well as **thathimthathimña** (such and such a...), which, when animate, should have **-mha** (**thathimhathathimha**, correlative of **gvamhagvamha**), which is not segmented off owing to the difficulty of breaking up the pronoun. **thvaleteti** (var. **thvaletiti**) “that/this much,” is a correlative of the adv.inter **gule** (how much?).

p.indef

Indefinite pronouns. This tag is used for indefinite pronouns, which begin with **su**, **chu**, or **gu** (var. **gva**) with any intervening case marker, followed by **-nam** (var. **no**). For example, **sunam** (var. **sunum**; “anyone”), or, with the genitive case marker **suyānam** (“anyone’s”). Stand-alone indefinite pronouns include **sum** (“nobody”), **humhum** (“some,” “the one or the other”), **gulichim** (“some”, var. **gulechinam**), and **ubhe** (“both”).

p.interrog

Interrogative pronouns. This tag is for the interrogative pronouns, which begin with **su-** (“who”) and **chu-** (“what”), and may take any case marker. When used in the interrogative (rather than correlative sense), **gvamham** (“which”) fits into this category.

p.pers

Personal pronouns. This tag is used for singular personal pronouns. First-person pronouns begin **ji** (var. **je**), and either alone or with the agreement markers **-gu** or **-guli**, can take a genitive meaning without a genitive case marker. A rare variant is **gejuli**. Second pronouns begin **cha**, **chana**, **chi** (var. **che**), **chala** and **chalapola**—the latter is an honourific plural but singular in meaning.

p.pers.pl

Plural personal pronouns. This tag is used for plural personal pronouns. The first person features an exclusive and inclusive system. The first-person exclusive is **jepani** (var. **jipani**), and the first person inclusive is **jheje** (vars. **jhejhe**, **jhiji**), without a need for **pani**. The second-person plural is **chesakala** (var. **cheskala**) and the second-person plural intimate is **cheje**. The third-person plural pronouns are **thvapani** (near speaker) and **vapani** (distant).

p.refl

Reflexive pronoun. This tag is used for the pronouns **thava**, **thavo** (“own,” “their own”), which are actually more like possessive pronouns. It is also used for **thama**, meaning “oneself” or “himself.”

p.rel

Relative pronoun. This tag is used for relative pronouns, usually combined with correlative pronouns. They begin with **chu** (“which”) or **su** (“who”) followed by case markers. Definite relatives begin with a form of **go** (var. **gva**), **gona**, or **gonakhu**. When animate, **mha** (var. **mhaṃ**, **mhā**), must precede the case marker.

Verbs

This section will give brief explanations of the verb forms denoted by tags, followed by some examples. The Roman numerals next to verbs in these examples indicate the verb class to which the example verbs belong. Regarding some of the absences, auxiliaries are treated according to their conjugation; copulas such as **ju**, **du**, and **khu** are treated as imperfective stative forms.

v.co

Coverb. This tag is used for the coverb, which Otter (§149) defines by saying that “in contrast to converbs, whose main function is to form the head of a subordinated VP, the coverb is usually only used in conjunction with an auxiliary verb... In some rare circumstances, the coverb can fulfil the same function as the circumstantial coverb [cv.cir].” The verbs defined as “auxiliaries,” which we do not tag as such, are **cone** (“to stay”), **juye** (“to become”), **taye** (“to put”), **bijyāye** (“to come (hon.)”), **yene** (“to lead”), **vane** (“to go”), **vaye** (“to come”), **haye** (“to bring” or “to carry”), and **gāye** (“to suffice”). The coverb generally carries a durative meaning (-ing), but interpretation can vary depending on the auxiliary verb with which it is used. It is formed by the ending **-seṃ** (var. **-syam**), **-se** (var. **-sya**), or **-aṃ** (var. **-oṃ**) added to the zero-grade stem, and first-grade stem in Class IV. In old Newar, e.g. *Gopalarājavamśavalī*, it is often used simply as a finite verb without an auxiliary.

E.g.

khasēṃ, **khañāṃ** (I)

dasēṃ, **jusyāṃ** (var. **juseṃ**) (II)

bisēṃ (var. **bisyāṃ**) (III)

ñhelasēṃ (IV)

khojalapaṃ (V)

v.dhak

Dhakam. This tag is used for the verb **dhakam**, which is the perfect past of **dhāye** (“to say”), which takes on the function of a dialogue marker, like the Sanskrit *iti*, or a marker of purpose, “in order to.” In the case of a dialogue maker, it is best left untranslated or indicated simply with quotation marks (in any case, it is usually followed by a regular verb which is translatable, such as in the case of **dhakam dhāyāva** (,” having said that) or **dhakam ñeñāva** (,” having heard that)).

v.ipv

Imperative. This tag is used for imperative verbs. This takes on several forms.

In the low-grade honourific case, it is the unmodified verb stem:

E.g.

yā (II)

dhā (III)

There are irregular low-grade honourific forms for **taye**: **te**, **ti**, for **haye**: **he**, **hi**, for **vaye**: **vā** (var. **va**).

In the middle-grade honourific case, it sees **-va** (var. **o**) or **-a** added to the zero grade, or **ñ** in class I:

E.g.

ñeño, **ñeña** (I)

yāva (II)

juva (III)

dayaki, **dayakina** (V)

In the high-grade honourific case, it sees **-hune** (var. **-huni**, **-huna**), **-guna** and rarely **-ñāna** added to the zero-grade stem:

E.g.

ñehuna, **ñeñāna** (I)

yāhune, **yāñāna** (II)

bihuna, **biñāna** (III)

The second-grade stem may also be modified:

E.g.

vaneguna (I)

senahuni, **selāhana**, **solahuni** (III)

There are also irregular high-grade honourific forms for **ju**: **jusane**, **jusana** (usually following **prasanna** (var. **prasanna**)).

Note also the irregular forms for **tolate** (var. **toḍate**; “abandon”): **tolatene** and **tolatine**, and the irregular form for **tāthe** (“to leave behind”): **tāthi**.

A first-person plural imperative (“let’s”) sees **-nu** added to the verb-noun (v.n) form of the verb, e.g. **phoṃne** (“to ask”) becomes **phoṃnenu** (“let us ask”).

v.impst

Imperfective/stative. This tag is used for verbs in the imperfective/stative. Otter (§47–8) describes this as having weak temporal deixis, “but in narrative contexts it is more often than not used with past reference... Like the perfective past, the stative participle is rarely used in contexts where the past conjunct form would be obligatory in Modern Newar... In these cases, the perfective participle is usually substituted.” This sees **-a** added to the zero grade stem of the verb, with allomorph **-ña**, **-ka**, and **-vo** for grades I, II, and III, respectively.

E.g.

khaña (I)

yāka (rare var. **yāna**) (II)

juvo (III)

māla (IV)

For some verbs, the imperfective stative is expressed with the suffix **-gva**, e.g. **coṃgva** (vars. **coṃgu**, **cvamṃgu**, **cvoṃgu**, etc.). Irregular stative forms with **-u** on the initial consonant of stems exist for **date**, **khaye**, and **juye**, and are often used as copulae, **du**, **khu**, and **ju**, respectively.

v.n

Verbal noun. This tag is used for the verbal noun, that is, roughly speaking, a non-past participle or infinitive. This sees **-e** added to the first grade of the verb stem in class I and the zero grade in other classes. This form is close to the modern future conjunct. Moreover, in manuscripts, the **-ye** is often written only as **-ya**, which should be carefully distinguished from v.impst by the presence of first grade in class I and the lack of allomorphs (**-ña**, **-ka**, and **-vo/va**) in the other classes added to the zero stem.

E.g.

khane (I)

juye (var. **juya**) (II)

yāye (var. **yāya**) (III)

māle (IV)

When used with oblique cases, the v.n takes on a form that looks like the v.perf.part, i.e. **-ā** followed by the case marker (e.g. **tayāyā** (**tayā**/v.n **yā**/case.gen), or **chedarapāyā** (**chedarapā**/v.n **yā**/case.gen)). In *Maṇicūḍa*, we see **yāyāṃ** (2B); Lienhard seems to identify this as a form of v.n (**yāyāṃ** = **yāye**) (p. 60f2).

v.np

Non-past verbs. This tag is used for non-past verbs, which express future actions, habitual or recurring actions in the present, or simply present actions. It sees **-i** added to the first-grade stem, but this can be extended to **-iva** in any class, **u** (var. **uva**) in classes II and II, and **-ino** or **-uno** in class III only. It is close to the modern future disjunct.

Eg.

khāniva (I)

yāyi, **yāyiva**, **yāyu**, **yāyuva** (II)

juyi, **juyiva**, **juyino**, **juyu**, **juyuva**, **juyuno**, rarely **java** (III)

māлива (IV) (Old variant: **mālu**).

v.perf.part

Perfective participle. This tag is used for verbs in the form of a perfective participle. Otter (§90–1) notes that this form is used as a finite conjunct verb and can serve as the head of an attributive verb phrase; it usually expresses an action that was completed in the past. This form sees **-ā** added to the first grade of the stem. Jørgensen (§126) notes that it can be used (1) as a relative participle, translated by the passive and used both attributively and substantively, (2) together with verbs like **khañe** (“to see;” e.g., **coke hora tayā khañāva**, “having seen that the rice had been strewn”) and **ñeñe** (“to hear;” e.g., **thathe barakhunina dhāyā ñeñāva**, “having heard the pigeon speak thus”), (3) as a verbal noun for completed action (e.g. **syanakā**, “the destruction”), and (4) predictively for the 1st and 2nd person (conjunct) as a subject, and as a past (e.g., **rājā ñhila. ji ñhilā**, “the king laughed; I laughed”). It is thus used as a conjunct in Classical Newar and continues to be used as the conjunct in contemporary Newar.

E.g.

khanā (I)

yāñā (II)

juyā (III)

mālā (IV)

v.perf.past

Perfective past. This tag is used for verbs in the perfective past. Otter (§38–9) notes that it is used with past reference for completed actions and is predominant in narrative. It is typically used as a disjunct past, and thus, in first and second-person declarative or interrogative sentences, the v.perf.part is used instead as a conjunct. This form sees **-aṃ** (var. **-oṃ**), **-a**, (var. **-o**) added to the first-grade stem of the verb. **-ā** occurs in Bhaktapur variants, which can be easily mistaken for a perfective participle (Jørgensen suggests this is just an error (§118)). Jørgensen (§117) calls this the “finite verb,” which denotes a completed action, and notes that it can be used (1) as the usual narrative form and (2) denoting “a future action, about the accomplishment of which there can be no doubt.”

E.g.

khanam (vars. **khana, khano, khanom**) (I)

yātam (vars. **yāta, yāto, yātom**) (II)

julam (vars. **jula, julo, julom, jura**) (III)

mālam (vars. **mala, malo, malom**) (IV)

v.rel.part

Relative participle. This tag is used for verbs in the form of a relative participle. Otter (§97) notes that this has two functions (1) stating attribution in the same way as the stative participle (v.impst) with no overt temporal deixis but with a degree of definitiveness, and (2) it can function as the head of a noun phrase as a relative noun. Jørgensen (§128) notes that its uses are as (1) a relative participle, (2) a verbal noun, and (3) a predicate (e.g. **jambuka sikva**, “the gazelle died”). It sees **-kom** (vars. **-kvaṃ, -ko, -kva, -ku**) added to the zero grade stem in classes I-III and the first-grade stem in classes IV and V.

E.g.

sekom (I)

yākom (II)

hakom (III)

mālakom (var. **mālako**) (IV)

bhālapakom (V)

Converbs

Converbs in Newar are non-finite verbs that sit in a temporal (e.g. after doing, having done) or conditional or concessive relationship (e.g. although doing) to a finite verb. These are participle forms with a case marker, and thus Jørgensen calls them conjunctive participles (e.g. §127), and they are not marked for tense or mode, which should be inferred from the finite verb. Therefore, converbs in Newar imply a different part of speech than Tibetan converbs, where the tag cv.X refers to a particle that turns the preceding verb into a converb.

cv.advs

Adversative converb. This tag is used for a converb, which expresses the meaning of “although doing X...” This sees **-aṃ** added to the causal converb (cv.caus), which has an intervening **-ān-** or **-an-**.

E.g.

juyānaṃ, dhāyānaṃ, soṇanaṃ (III)

cv.ant

Antecedent converb. This tag is used for the converb which expresses an action completed prior to the finite verb, in the sense of “having done X...” It sees **-āva** (vars. **-āvo**, **-āo**) added to the first grade of the stem.

E.g.

khañāva (I)**yāñāva** (II)**biyāva** (III)**ñhelāva** (IV)

cv.anter

Anterior converb. This tag is used for a converb identified created by the postposition **li**, which is what receives the tag, the sense being given one of time having passed since the converb’s action was completed, e.g. “after doing X.” To create this construction, **li** follows a cv.caus or cv.advs, or zero stem plus **-sena** or **-senaṃ**, in which case, they receive this tag too (we do not have examples of this in our corpus yet). It is also paired with v.co **jusyamaṃ** (e.g. **jusyamaṃ li**).

E.g.

vāñāna li (var. **vāñānaṃ li**) (I)**yāñāna li** (var. **yāñānaṃ li**) (II)**dhāsena li** (var. **dhāsenaṃ li**) (III)

cv.as

As converb. This tag is used for the converb that creates an ingressive sense that the following action occurs when the previous one occurs or at the same time (i.e. “as doing ...”). This sees **-ñāseṃ** (var. **-ñāsyamaṃ**), **-ñāse** (var. **-ñāsyā**), or **-ñāna** added to the second-grade stem. An unusual form appears to be expressed with **yāuṃsyā** (Mañicūḍa 2A, 3A), this sense can also be carried by the postposition **-thyamaṃ**.

E.g.

tānañāseṃ (I)**yātañāna** (II)**valañāseṃ, valañāna** (III)**socakalañāseṃ** (V)

cv.caus

Causal converb. This tag is used for a converb that expresses an action that causes or is instrumental to, the finite verb. It does this by the addition of an ergative/ablative marker **-ana** (var. **-āna**) to the stative (v.impst) or perfective participle (v.perf.part).

E.g.

kāñāna, kāyāna (I)

yāñana, yāñāna (II)
dhavana, dhayāna (III)
socakuna (V)

cv.cir

Circumstantial converb. This tag is used for a converb that expresses action circumstantial to the finite verb, with the sense of “in a way that X” (e.g. **mevana ma kṇanakam chalapola je samīpasa bijyāye māla**, “You must come to me *without being seen* by anyone else”). It does this by seeing **-am** added to the causative stem **-k-**.

E.g.

kṇanakam (I)
phuyakam (II)

cv.coex

Coextensive converb. This tag is used for a converb that expresses an action that occurs coextensive with the action of the finite verb, i.e. “as long as X...”. It does this by having **-tole** (var. **-tola**), **-tote** to the zero stem, with **-na** sometimes being added on the end.

E.g.

vatolena (I)
datolena, dvātola (var. **dvātota**) (II)
dhātole, lhātolana (III)

cv.coin

Coincident converb. This tag is used for a converb that expresses imperfective background action, i.e. “while doing X...”. It is formed by adding **-le** or **-lem** to the zero grade stem or the first grade for class V. In class I, **-na** and **-va** may be added without any change in meaning.

E.g.

mhale (vars. **mhalena, mhaleva**) (I)
yāle (II)
sole (III)
yācakale (V)

cv.cond.caus

Causal conditional converb. This tag is used for a converb that expresses a causal or conditional relationship between the converb and finite verb of the sense “When X is done...” or “If X...” It does this by adding **-ñāsa** to the second-grade stem.

E.g.

ñeñāsa (I)
yāñāsa, yātañāsa (II)
biyāsa, bilañāsa (III)

cv.cond

Conditional converb. This tag is used for a converb that expresses a condition that the converb must fulfil so that the finite verb be the case, i.e. “if X...” It sees **-sā** added to the second-grade stem of class I–III verbs, and the third-grade stem of class V verbs.

E.g.

vanasā (I)
yātasā (II)
bilasā (III)
mocakalasā (V)

cv.neg

Negative converb. This tag is used for a converb that expresses a negative condition that may be obtained before the action of the finite verb, i.e. “even if X...” It is formed by adding **-sanam** (var. **-sanam**) to the second-grade stem of classes I-IV and the third-grade stem of class V.

E.g.

khanasanom (I)
datasanom (II)
julasanom (III)
mālasanam (IV)
mocakalasanom (V)

cv.pre.ant

Preceding antecedent converb. This tag is used for a converb, which expresses that the action of the finite verb occurs immediately after that of the converb. It sees **-tunom**, **-stunom** (var. **-stunam**) added to the zero grade stem or the verb-noun (v.n) form.

E.g.

khastunom (vars. **khanetunom**, **khanestunom**) (I)
yāstunam (II)
dhāstunam (vars. **dhāyatunom**, **dhāyastunom**) (III)

cv.red

Reduplicating converb. This tag is used for a converb with reduplication, which characterises the action in the converb as ongoing or repetitive and having a causal relationship to the finite verb. It sees the reduplication of the zero grade stem and **-na**, **-sem**, or **-m** suffixed.

E.g.

ñeñem (I)
lvālvām (II)
soṃsoṃ, sesenam (III)

cv.ass

Associative converb. This tag is used for a converb that expresses a weaker conditionality than the conditional converb, i.e. “when...” rather than “if...” It sees **-ñāva** added to the second-grade stem and thus is based on the use of the associative ending **-va**, perhaps with the sense of “with the doing of X...”

E.g.

jonañāva (I)
datañāva (II)
valañāva (III)
gocakalañāva (V)

cv.temp

Temporal converb. This tag is used for a converb, which expresses that the finite verb occurs after what precedes the cv.temp with the use of a negative **ma**, i.e. “Finite verb Y occurred before *X would occur*” (e.g. *sūryodaya ma jubala kheṃ cāye*, “he washed his face before the sunrise” or literally “the sunrise did not occur when he washed his face.” It sees **ma** before the stem verb, which takes **-bala** or **-vala**, most commonly **ma jubala**. The **ma** is to be tagged neg, whereas the **jubala** is to be tagged cv.temp.

cv.term

Terminal converb. This tag is used for a converb, which expresses that the finite verb will occur *until* the action in the converb is complete. It sees the negative **ma** with the verb stem suffixed by **-tolena**. E.g. *va lihā ma vatolena chalapolasake sisem taye*, “*Until he comes back*, I shall entrust her to your care.”

Others

conj

Conjunctions. This tag is used for conjunctions, such as **va**, meaning both “and” and “or,” depending on the context. Occasionally, **-nam** (var. **-na**) can be translated as “also,” but is used in much the same way as the cl.focus.

encl

Enclitics. This tag is used for enclitics, such as **ādi** and **ādina**, meaning “et cetera.”

evid

Evidential. This tag is used for the evidential particle **khama**, which indicates that what precedes it is evidential. This also is used for **thukā** (“as it is known”).

interj

Interjections. This tag is used for interjections, such as **bho**, “O,” and **jā** “after all/you know.”

neg

Negative. This tag is used for the negative particle **ma**. Before forms of **māle** and **mvāle**, it is sometimes written **mu**, e.g. **mu mvāla**.

skt

Sanskrit. This tag is used for Sanskrit when used entirely within Sanskrit sentences, we do not attempt also to perform POS tagging for Sanskrit. Since Newar consists largely of Sanskrit nouns and even verb stems based on Sanskrit, this tag can sometimes result in misidentifications within the body of our Newar texts. For the most part, this should be confined to maṅgalam verses or colophons, however.

There are some exceptions, where a term is clearly Sanskrit and may even be conjugated but appears to be used in an otherwise entirely Newar sentence. In the *Gopālarājjavamśavalī*, this includes **dinaḥ**, which appears to be adverbially used to mean “it was the day that...” with the rest of the sentence being what occurred that day (it is tagged adv.temp; it is more or less parallel in meaning to

divasa), and **jātaḥ/jāta**, which would be the past participle of the Sanskrit **jan**, birth, but appears to be used in conjunction with a case.gen in the sense of “there was the birth of...” and is tagged as n.

nep

Nepāli. This tag is used for Nepali text that is usually inserted by editors of editions.

unknown

Unknown. This tag is used for terms that we absolutely don’t know. While we usually try to opt on the side of a most-likely guess, there are times when this is impossible, such as unknown words or forms, damaged manuscripts, or obscured writing.

punc

Punctuation. This tag is used for daṇḍas, double daṇḍas, commas, periods, or any other punctuation which may be introduced in editions or used in manuscripts.

fol

Folio. This tag is used for folio numbers or page numbers. Since it will be obvious whether it is a folio or page by the presence of a letter after the number (e.g. r or v for recto and verso, or sometimes a and b), we see no need for an additional tag for edition pages.

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